

Thrips (Insecta: Thysanoptera) of India- An Updated Checklist

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Abstract

An updated checklist of Thysanoptera from India is provided with their distribution data. In total 739 species in 259 genera are listed of which 309 species in 116 genera of suborder Terebrantia and 430 species in 143 genera of suborder Tubulifera. Forty four species with new distributional records are provided for different geographical regions of India.

Key Words: India, list, species, Thysanoptera

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Introduction

Insect order Thysanoptera with two suborders Terebrantia and Tubulifera, encompasses about 6102 species in eight families across the globe. The Terebrantia is known by about 2500 species, whereas the Tubulifera covers more than 3600 species from all over the world (ThripsWiki 2016).

Ramakrishna Ayyar, T. V. probably was the first to start taxonomy of these little insects in India. He along with Margabandhu V. has recorded 232 species of Thysanoptera from India in their catalogue which was published in 1940.

Ananthkrishnan & Sen (1980) listed 659 species of 253 genera of Thysanoptera in which 266 species of 110 genera of Terebrantia and 393 species of 143 genera. Later on, Bhatti (1990) catalogued 290 species of 124 genera of Terebrantia in 5 families from Indian subregion.

Further Sen (1980), Sen et al. (1988, 2000), Bhatti et al. (2006), Bhatti & Ranganath (2006), Bhatti (1997), Kumar et al. (2005a, 2005b, 2007), Kumar & Tyagi (2007), Tyagi et al. (2008), Tyagi & Kumar (2008a, 2008b) are some of the major studies which have substantially added a

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number of species to the Thysanoptera from India. These studies have substantially increased the number of species known from India, totaling 739 species in 259 genera belonging to six families. Out of which Terebrantia contains 309 species in 116 genera in five families: Aeolothripidae (17 species of 9 genera), Merothripidae (3 species of 2 genera), Melanthripidae (3 species of one genus), Stenurothripidae (2 species of one genus), Thripidae (284 species of 103 genera) and Tubulifera with 430 species of 143 genera in its sole family Phlaeothripidae. The objective of this paper is to provide up to date list on thrips fauna of India with distribution records.

The Checklist

Full synonymies for the names listed here are available on the web (ThripsWiki). Distribution records of species are based on Ananthakrishnan & Sen (1980), Bhatti (1990, 1997), recent publication of the authors. The symbol (*) indicates new distributional record from different geographical part of India for the species.

Family Aeolothripidae

Aduncothrips Ananthakrishnan 1964

Aduncothrips asiaticus (Ramakrishana and Margabandhu 1931). Distribution: India (Karnataka, Tamil Nadu).

Aeolothrips Haliday 1836

Aeolothrips collaris Priesner 1919.
Distribution: India (Bihar, Delhi,

Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).

Aeolothrips distinctus Bhatti 1971.
Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh).

Aeolothrips indicus Bhatti 1964.
Distribution: India (Punjab).

Aeolothrips intermedius Bagnall 1934.
Distribution: India (Punjab).

Aeolothrips mongolicus Pelikán 1985.
Distribution: India (Delhi, Uttar Pradesh*).

Aeolothrips moundi Kulshrestha & Vijay Veer 1984. Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Aeolothrips nigricornis Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Allelothrips Bagnall 1932

Allelothrips pandyani (Ramakrishna and Margabandhu 1931). Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).

Franklinothrips Back 1912

Franklinothrips megalops Trybom 1912.
Distribution: India (West Bengal, Odisha*, Tamil Nadu).

Franklinothrips uttarakhandiensis Vijay Veer 2010. Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

Franklinothrips vespiformis (Crawford, D.L. 1909). Distribution: India (Chhattisgarh, Karnataka, Maharashtra*, Tamil Nadu*).

Gelothrips Bhatti 1967

Gelothrips cinctus (Hood 1918).
Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).

Indothrips Bhatti 1967

Indothrips bhushani Bhatti 1967.
Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka,

Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh).

Mymarothrips Bagnall 1928

Mymarothrips garuda Ramakrishna and Margabandhu 1931. Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal*).

Orothrips Moulton 1907

Orothrips yosemitii Moulton 1911. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Streothrips Bhatti 1971

Streothrips arorai (Bhatti 1967). Distribution: India (Karnataka*, Madhya Pradesh).

Family Melanthripidae Bagnall

Melanthrips Haliday 1836

Melanthrips affluens Ananthakrishnan 1966. Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Melanthrips baileyi Ananthakrishnan 1965. Distribution: India (Goa-Karnataka Broader).

Melanthrips indicus Bhatti 1967. Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).

Family Merothripidae Hood

Erotidothrips Priesner 1939

Erotidothrips mirabilis Priesner 1939. Distribution: India (Kerala).

Merothrips Hood 1912

Merothrips indicus Bhatti & Ananthakrishnan 1975. Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal*).

Merothrips morgani Hood 1912. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Family Stenurothripidae

Holarthrothrips Bagnall 1927

Holarthrothrips indicus Bhatti & Ananthakrishnan 1978. Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab).

Holarthrothrips jambudvipae (Ramakrishna 1928). Distribution: India (Karnataka, Tamil Nadu).

Family Thripidae Stephens

Subfamily Dendrothripinae

Asprothrips J. C. Crawford 1938

Asprothrips indicus (Bagnall 1919). Distribution: India (Kerala).

Asprothrips navsariensis Tyagi 2011. Distribution: India (Gujarat).

Dendrothrips Uzel 1895

Dendrothrips albus Bhatti 1967. Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).

Dendrothrips aspersus Bhatti 1971. Distribution: India (Jammu & Kashmir).

Dendrothrips cameroni Priesner 1965. Distribution: India (Delhi).

Dendrothrips cibarius Ananthakrishnan 1965. Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Dendrothrips elixae Bhatti 1971. Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Dendrothrips faurei Bhatti 1971. Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Dendrothrips jasminum (Ramakrishna and Margabandhu 1939). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Dendrothrips mendax Bhatti 1971. Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Dendrothrips minutus (Ananthakrishnan 1961). Distribution: India (Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh).

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Dendrothrips punctatus zur Strassen 1968.

Distribution: India (Delhi, Tamil Nadu).

Dendrothrips saltator Uzel 1895.

Distribution: India (Jammu & Kashmir).

Dendrothrips sexmaculatus Bagnall 1916.

Distribution: India (Karnataka, Kerala, West Bengal).

Dendrothrips stannardi (Ananthakrishnan 1958). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Dendrothrips strasseni Bhatti 1971.

Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh).

***Leucothrips* Reuter, 1904**

Leucothrips nigripennis Reuter, 1904.

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

***Parsiiothrips* Bhatti 1970**

Parsiiothrips fuscus Bhatti 1970.

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

***Projectothripoides* Shumsher 1942**

Projectothripoides pandai (Shumsher 1942).

Distribution: India (Odisha).

***Pseudodendrothrips* Schmutz 1913**

Pseudodendrothrips albana Bhatti 1997.

Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka).

Pseudodendrothrips bhattii Kudo 1984.

Distribution: India (Karnataka, Tamil Nadu).

Pseudodendrothrips kulshresthai Chauhan & Vijay Veer, 1992. Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

Pseudodendrothrips mori (Niwa 1908).

Distribution: (Karnataka).

Pseudodendrothrips ornatissimus Schmutz 1913. Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal)

Pseudodendrothrips suvarna Bhatti 1997.

Distribution: India (Delhi, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Uttar Pradesh*).

Subfamily Panchaetothripinae

***Astrothrips* Karny 1921**

Astrothrips asiaticus (Bhatti 1967).

Distribution: India (Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Astrothrips globiceps (Karny 1913).

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Astrothrips lantana Bhatti 1967.

Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).

Astrothrips paroilimbus Stannard & Mitri 1962. Distribution: India (Andamans, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Astrothrips stannardi Bhatti 1967.

Distribution: India (Delhi, Haryana, Punjab*, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh*)

Astrothrips tumiceps Karny 1923.

Distribution: India (Delhi*, Karnataka*, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab*, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh*, West Bengal*).

***Caliothrips* Daniel 1904**

Caliothrips graminicola (Bagnall & Cameron 1932). Distribution: India (Delhi, Jammu & Kashmir, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal, widely distributed).

Caliothrips impurus (Priesner 1928).

Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).

Caliothrips indicus (Bagnall 1913).

Distribution: India (Delhi*, south of Himalaya, Karnataka*, West Bengal, widely distributed).

Caliothrips luckmanni Wilson 1975.

Distribution: India (Delhi, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal*).

Caliothrips sudanensis (Bagnall & Cameron 1932). Distribution: India.

Euidothrips Ananthakrishnan 1968

Euidothrips apsarus Ananthakrishnan 1968.

Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).

Helionothrips Bagnall 1932

Helionothrips aino (Ishida 1931).

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Helionothrips kadaliphilus (Ramakrishna and Margabandhu 1931). Distribution:

India (Kerala, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Helionothrips nilgircus (Ananthakrishnan 1967). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Helionothrips parvus Bhatti 1968.

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Helionothrips shivalik Bhatti 2006.

Distribution: India (Punjab).

Heliothrips Haliday 1836

Heliothrips haemorrhoidalis (Bouché 1833).

Distribution: India (Andamans, Karnataka, Kerala, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu).

Hercinothrips Bagnall 1932

Hercinothrips bicinctus (Bagnall 1919).

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Monilothrips Moulton 1929

Monilothrips kempi Moulton 1929.

Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Noathrips Bhatti 1967

Noathrips prakashi Bhatti 1967.

Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).

Panchaetothrips Bagnall 1912

Panchaetothrips noxius Priesner 1937.

Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

Panchaetothrips indicus Bagnall 1912.

Distribution: India (Assam, Bihar, Goa, Haryana, Kerala, Manipur, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).

Parthenothrips Uzel 1895

Parthenothrips dracaenae (Heeger 1854).

Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).

Phibalothrips Hood 1918

Phibalothrips peringueyi (Faure 1925).

Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, widely distributed).

Retithrips Marchal 1910

Retithrips syriacus (Mayet 1890).

Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Goa, Karnataka*, Kerala, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal)

Rhipiphorothrips Morgan 1913

Rhipiphorothrips cruentatus Hood

1919. Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Assam, Delhi, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh*, West Bengal).

Rhipiphorothrips pulchellus Morgan 1913.

Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh, West Bengal*, Delhi*).

Selenothrips Karny 1911

Selenothrips rubrocinctus (Giard 1901).

Distribution: India (Andaman Island,

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Assam, Karnataka, Kerala, Manipur, Meghalaya, West Bengal).

Tryphacothrips Bagnall 1919

Tryphacothrips rutherfordi (Bagnall 1915).

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Zaniothrips Bhatti 1967

Zaniothrips ricini Bhatti 1967. Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh, West Bengal).

Subfamily Sericothripinae

Hydatothrips Karny 1913

Hydatothrips ananthakrishnani Bhatti 1973.

Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).

Hydatothrips atactus Bhatti 1973.

Distribution: India (Delhi).

Hydatothrips aureus Bhatti 1973.

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Hydatothrips boerhaaviae Seshadri & Ananthakrishnan 1954. Distribution: India (Delhi, Jammu & Kashmir, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh).

Hydatothrips dorax Bhatti 1973.

Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).

Hydatothrips hartwigi (Bhatti 1973).

Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).

Hydatothrips proximus Bhatti 1973.

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Uttarakhand).

Hydatothrips ramaswamiahi Priesner 1926.

Distribution: India (Delhi, Haryana, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu).

Neohydatothrips John 1929

Neohydatothrips gracilipes (Hood 1924).
Distribution: India (Chandigarh, Delhi, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu).

Neohydatothrips latis (Bhatti 1973).
Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Neohydatothrips plynopygus (Karny, 1925).
Distribution: India (Kerala).

Neohydatothrips raniae (Bhatti 1967).
Distribution: India (Delhi, Uttar Pradesh).

Neohydatothrips samayunkur Kudô 1995.
Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Manipur, Uttarakhand).

Subfamily Thripinae

Abacothrips Bhatti 1986

Abacothrips lotus Bhatti 1986. Distribution: India (Jammu & Kashmir).

Agalmothrips Priesner 1965

Agalmothrips parviceps (Priesner 1965).
Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Agriothrips Ananthakrishnan 1966

Agriothrips brevisetosus Ananthakrishnan 1966. Distribution: India (Kerala).

Ajothrips Bhatti 1967

Ajothrips gara Bhatti 1967. Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Ajothrips karma Bhatti 1967. Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Ajothrips medius Bhatti 1997. Distribution: India (Delhi).

Akheta Bhatti 1978

Akheta indica Bhatti 1999. Distribution: India (Kerala).

Alathrips Bhatti 1970

- Alathrips roonwali* (Bhatti 1963). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Gujarat, Rajasthan).
- Amalothrips*** Ananthakrishnan 1967
Amalothrips flaccidus Ananthakrishnan 1967. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Amphithrips*** Ananthakrishnan 1965
Amphithrips argutus Ananthakrishnan 1965. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).
- Anaphothrips*** Uzel 1895
Anaphothrips latis Bhatti 1967. Distribution: India (Maharashtra).
Anaphothrips obscurus (Müller 1776). Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir).
Anaphothrips sudanensis Trybom 1911. Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka, Meghalaya, Punjab, Sikkim, West Bengal, widely distributed).
- Anascirtothrips*** Bhatti 1961
Anascirtothrips arorai Bhatti 1961. Distribution: India (Delhi, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).
- Aneurothrips*** Karny 1912
Aneurothrips priesneri Bhatti 1971. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Aptinothrips*** Haliday 1836
Aptinothrips rufus (Haliday 1836). Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).
- Aptinothrips stylifer* Trybom 1894. Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).
- Aroidothrips*** Ananthakrishnan 1960
Aroidothrips longistylus Ananthakrishnan 1960. Distribution: India (Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).
- Arorathrips*** Bhatti 1990
Arorathrips mexicanus (D. L. Crawford 1909). Distribution: India (Karnataka*, Kerala, Tamil Nadu).
- Ayyaria*** Karny 1927
Ayyaria chaetophora Karny 1927. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha*, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).
- Bacathrips*** Bhatti 1990
Bacathrips solanifolii (Shumsher 1944). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Bathrips*** Bhatti 1962
Bathrips jasminae Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India (Karnataka, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu).
Bathrips melanicornis (Shumsher 1946). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh*, West Bengal).
- Biltothrips*** Bhatti 1973
Biltothrips minutus (Bhatti 1967). Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, West Bengal).

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Bolacothrips Uzel 1895

Bolacothrips bicolor Ananthkrishnan 1960.

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Bolacothrips evittatus (Sakimura 1958).

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Bolacothrips indicus (Ananthkrishnan 1966). Distribution: India (Gujarat, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal*).

Bolacothrips striatopennatus (Schmutz 1913).

Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka*, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).

Bregmatothrips Hood 1912

Bregmatothrips binervis (Kobus 1893).

Distribution: India (Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).

Bregmatothrips brachycephalus (Shumsher 1942). Distribution: India (Delhi, Haryana, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu).

Capitothrips Bhatti 1974

Capitothrips subramanii Bhatti 1974.

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Caprithrips Faure 1933

Caprithrips ajanta Bhatti 1980. Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Caprithrips melanophthalmus (Bagnall 1927). Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir).

Caprithrips orientalis Bhatti 1973.

Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).

Ceratothripoides Bagnall 1918

Ceratothripoides claratris (Shumsher 1946).

Distribution: India (Delhi, Maharashtra, Odisha, Tamil Nadu).

Chaetanaphothrips Priesner 1925

Chaetanaphothrips leeuweni (Karny 1914).

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Chaetanaphothrips orchidii (Moulton 1907).

Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal*).

Chirothrips Haliday 1836

Chirothrips africanus Priesner 1932.

Distribution: India (Delhi, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu).

Chirothrips capensis zur Strassen 1958.

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Chirothrips maximi Ananthkrishnan 1957.

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Chirothrips meridionalis Bagnall 1927.

Distribution: India (Delhi, Punjab, Chandigarh, Delhi, Uttar Pradesh).

Craspedothrips zur Strassen 1966

Craspedothrips minor (Bagnall 1921).

Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Ctenidothrips Priesner 1952

Ctenidothrips bambusae Priesner 1952.

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Ctenothrips Franklin 1907

Ctenothrips barapatharensis Tyagi, Ghosh & Kumar (2014). Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Ctenothrips niger Kudo 1977. Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Ctenothrips smilax Bhatti 1976.

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir).

Danothrips Bhatti 1971

Danothrips setifer Bhatti 1971. Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Dendrothripoides Bagnall 1923

Dendrothripoides innoxius (Karny 1914). Distribution: India: (Delhi, Karnataka).

Diarthrothrips Williams 1915

Diarthrothrips nimbus (Ananthkrishnan 1965). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Delhi*, Karnataka*, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh*, Tamil Nadu).

Dichromothrips Priesner 1932

Dichromothrips corbetti (Priesner 1936). Distribution: India (Delhi).

Dichromothrips indicus Mound 1976. Distribution: India (Delhi, West Bengal).

Dichromothrips nakahari Mound 1976. Distribution: India (Meghalaya, West Bengal).

Dichromothrips phalaenopsidis Sakimura 1955. Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Dichromothrips smithi (Zimmermann 1900). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Eremiothrips Priesner 1950

Eremiothrips antilope (Priesner 1923). Distribution: India (Rajasthan).

Eremiothrips varius (Bhatti 1967). Distribution: India (Delhi*).

Eremiothrips acutus (Bhatti 1972). Distribution: India (Haryana).

Ernothrips Bhatti 1967

Ernothrips immsi (Bagnall 1926). Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Ernothrips lobatus (Bhatti 1967). Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh).

Euphysothrips Bagnall 1926

Euphysothrips minozzii Bagnall 1926. Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu).

Euphysothrips subramanii (Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1939). Distribution: India (Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal*).

Exothrips Priesner 1939

Exothrips ananthkrishnani Bhatti 1975. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Exothrips anolis (Bhatti 1967). Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).

Exothrips cephalicus Bhatti 1975. Distribution: India (Delhi, Madhya Pradesh).

Exothrips deemax Bhatti 1975. Distribution: India (Delhi).

Exothrips hemavarna (Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1931). Distribution: India (Chandigarh, Delhi, Haryana, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh*, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Exothrips jammuensis Vijay Veer & Srivastava 1985. Distribution: India (Jammu & Kashmir).

Exothrips ornus Bhatti 1975. Distribution: India (Delhi).

Exothrips poorva Bhatti 1975. Distribution: India (Delhi).

Exothrips redox Bhatti 1975. Distribution: India (Delhi, Jammu & Kashmir, Punjab).

Exothrips sacchari (Moulton 1936). Distribution: India (Punjab).

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- Exothrips sakimurai* (Ananthakrishnan 1961). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Exothrips shweta Bhatti & Ananthakrishnan 1978. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Florithrips* Bhatti 1970**
Florithrips traegardhi (Trybom 1911). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh*).
- Foliothrips* Bhatti 1972**
Foliothrips oratus Bhatti 1972. Distribution: India (Delhi, Maharashtra).
- Frankliniella* Karny 1910**
Frankliniella insularis (Franklin 1908). Distribution: India.
Frankliniella intonsa (Trybom 1895). Distribution: India (Bihar, West Bengal, Meghalaya).
Frankliniella occidentalis (Pergande 1895). Distribution: India (Karnataka).
Frankliniella schultzei (Trybom 1910). Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Delhi, Karnataka, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).
Frankliniella unicolor Morgan 1925. Distribution: India (Kerala).
- Fulmekiola* Karny 1925**
Fulmekiola serrata (Kobus 1892). Distribution: India (Haryana, Punjab, Uttar Pradesh).
- Gnomonothrips* Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1939**
Gnomonothrips coimbatorensis Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1939. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Indusiothrips* Priesner 1952**
Indusiothrips seshadri Priesner 1952. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Jakthrips* Bhatti & Ranganath 2006**
Jakthrips ignacimuthui Bhatti & Ranganath 2006. Distribution: India (Karnataka).
- Kurtomathrips* Moulton 1927**
Kurtomathrips morrilli Moulton 1927. Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka).
- Laplothrips* Bhatti 1972**
Laplothrips bicolor Bhatti 1972. Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).
- Lefroyothrips* Priesner 1938**
Lefroyothrips lefroyi (Bagnall 1913). Distribution: India (Assam, Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Uttarakhand, West Bengal).
Lefroyothrips obscurus (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1966). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Limothrips* Haliday 1836**
Limothrips cerealium (Haliday 1836). Distribution: The only recorded material from India is the head and prothorax of a single specimen from Coimbatore (Tamil Nadu) (Bhatti 1990: 238).
- Megalurothrips* Bagnall 1915**
Megalurothrips distalis (Karny 1913). Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh*, West Bengal).
Megalurothrips mucunae (Priesner 1938). Distribution: India (Assam).

Megalurothrips peculiaris (Bagnall 1918).
Distribution: India (Bihar, Delhi, Karnataka, Manipur, Meghalaya, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh).

Megalurothrips typicus Bagnall 1915.
Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu).

Megalurothrips usitatus (Bagnall 1913).
Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh).

Microcephalothrips Bagnall 1926

Microcephalothrips abdominalis (D. L. Crawford 1910). Distribution: India (Arunachal Pradesh, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh*, Karnataka, Meghalaya, Punjab, West Bengal).

Moundinothrips Bhatti 1999

Moundinothrips robustus (Bhatti 1995).
Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Punjab).

Mycterothrips Trybom 1910

Mycterothrips acaciae Priesner 1932.
Distribution: India (Haryana, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh*).

Mycterothrips chaetogastra (Ramakrishna 1934). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Mycterothrips nilgiriensis (Ananthakrishnan 1960). Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh).

Mycterothrips ricini (Shumsher 1946).
Distribution: India (Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan).

Mycterothrips setiventris (Bagnall 1918).
Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Neocorynothrips Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1939

Neocorynothrips asiaticus Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1939. Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Octothrips Moulton 1940

Octothrips bhattii (Wilson 1972).
Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).

Odontothrips Amyot & Serville, 1843

Odontothrips moringa Tyagi & Kumar 2016.
Distribution: India (Rajasthan).

Organothrips Hood 1940

Organothrips indicus Bhatti 1974.
Distribution: India (Delhi, Maharashtra, West Bengal).

Oxythrips Uzel 1895

Oxythrips indicus Bhatti 1967. Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Oxythrips kochummani Ananthakrishnan 1969. Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Palmiothrips Bhatti 1978

Palmiothrips palmae (Ramakrishna 1934).
Distribution: India (Karnataka, Tamil Nadu).

Parabaliiothrips Priesner 1935

Parabaliiothrips takahashii Priesner 1935.
Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Parexothrips Priesner 1965

Parexothrips capitis Bhatti 1975.
Distribution: India (Jammu & Kashmir).

Checklist-Thrips of India

- Parexothrips tenellus* (Priesner 1950).
Distribution: India (Delhi). Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).
- Rhamphothrips santokhi* Kulshrestha & Vijay Veer 1984. Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).
- Plutonothrips*** Priesner 1933
Plutonothrips cus (Bhatti 1967).
Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab, Uttar Pradesh).
- Priesneriola*** Ananthakrishnan 1964
Priesneriola oneillae Ananthakrishnan 1964.
Distribution: India (Delhi, Maharashtra, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh*, West Bengal).
- Projectothrips*** Moulton 1929
Projectothrips bhattii Ananthakrishnan 1973. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Projectothrips pruthi Moulton 1929.
Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).
- Psilothrips*** Hood 1927
Psilothrips indicus Bhatti 1967.
Distribution: India (Delhi).
- Rhamphothrips*** Karny 1913
Rhamphothrips aureus (Ananthakrishnan 1954). Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu).
Rhamphothrips bhattii Tyagi & Kumar 2013.
Distribution: India (Odisha, West Bengal).
Rhamphothrips jasminae (Bhatti 1977).
Distribution: India (Delhi, Kerala).
Rhamphothrips pardus (Bhatti 1967).
Distribution: India (West Bengal).
Rhamphothrips pandens Sakimura 1983.
Distribution: India.
Rhamphothrips parviceps (Hood 1919).
Distribution: India (Delhi, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).
- Salpingothrips*** Hood 1935
Salpingothrips hoodi Ananthakrishnan 1969.
Distribution: India (Delhi).
- Sciothrips*** Bhatti 1970
Sciothrips cardamomi (Ramakrishna 1935).
Distribution: India (Arunachal Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).
- Scirtothrips*** Shull 1909
Scirtothrips bispinosus (Bagnall 1924).
Distribution: India (Karnataka, Tamil Nadu).
Scirtothrips dorsalis Hood 1919.
Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Delhi, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).
Scirtothrips fulleri Faure 1929. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Scirtothrips kenyensis Mound 1968.
Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh)
Scirtothrips oligochaetus (Karny 1927).
Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh),
Scirtothrips mangiferae Priesner 1932.
Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh).
Scirtothrips pteridicola Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

***Scolothrips* Hinds 1902**

Scolothrips asura Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1931. Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Scolothrips rhagebianus Priesner 1950. Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka, West Bengal).

Scolothrips tenuipennis zur strassen 1965. Distribution: India (Delhi).

***Smeringothrips* Priesner 1938**

Smeringothrips salaciae Priesner 1938. Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).

***Smilothrips* Bhatti 1976**

Smilothrips productus Bhatti 1976. Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

***Sorghothrips* Priesner 1936**

Sorghothrips fuscus (Ananthakrishnan 1965). Distribution: India (Delhi, Haryana, Kerala).

Sorghothrips jonnaphilus (Ramakrishna 1928). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu).

***Sphaeropothrips* Priesner 1928**

Sphaeropothrips vittipennis (Bagnall 1927). Distribution: India (Haryana, Uttar Pradesh).

***Stenchaetothrips* Bagnall 1926**

Stenchaetothrips aralis Bhatti 1982. Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).

Stenchaetothrips bambusae (Shumsher 1946). Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu), Burma.

Stenchaetothrips bicolor (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1967). Distribution: India (Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu).

Stenchaetothrips biformis (Bagnall 1913). Distribution: India (Delhi, Chandigarh, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Odisha, Madhya Pradesh, Meghalaya, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, widely distributed).

Stenchaetothrips caulis Bhatti 1982. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Stenchaetothrips dissidens (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1967). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Stenchaetothrips divisae Bhatti 1982. Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Stenchaetothrips faurei (Bhatti 1962). Distribution: India (Delhi, Haryana, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Punjab, Uttar Pradesh).

Stenchaetothrips glandularis (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1967). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu, Tripura).

Stenchaetothrips graminis (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1967). Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Stenchaetothrips hullikali Tyagi & Kumar 2008. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Stenchaetothrips indicus (Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1931). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Punjab, West Bengal).

Stenchaetothrips minutus (van Deventer 1906). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Stenchaetothrips melaneurus Bagnall 1926. Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Stenchaetothrips pteratus Bhatti 1982. Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Stenchaetothrips sciurus Bhatti 1982. Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Checklist-Thrips of India

Stenchaetothrips spinulae Tyagi & Kumar 2008. Distribution: India (Karnataka, West Bengal).

Stenchaetothrips tenebricus (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1968). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Taeniothrips Amyot & Serville 1843

Taeniothrips bharakariensis Kumar & Tyagi 2014. Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Taeniothrips major Bagnall 1916. Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Uttar Pradesh).

Taeniothrips orchidi Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Taeniothrips tigris Bhatti 1995. Distribution: India.

Tameothrips Bhatti 1978

Tameothrips arundo Tyagi & Kumar 2015. Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Tenothrips Bhatti 1967

Tenothrips frici (Uzel 1895). Distribution: India (Delhi, Jammu & Kashmir).

Thrips Linnaeus 1758

Thrips alatus Bhatti 1980. Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Thrips andrewsi (Bagnall 1921). Distribution: India (Assam, Chandigarh, Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).

Thrips apicatus Priesner 1934. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh*, West Bengal).

Thrips arorai Bhatti 1980. Distribution: India (Punjab, Himachal Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh).

Thrips atactus Bhatti 1967. Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Thrips beharensis (Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1939). Distribution: India (Bihar, Sikkim, West Bengal).

Thrips carthami Shumsher 1946. Distribution: India (Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir).

Thrips cedri Bhatti 1980. Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Thrips chandni Bhatti 1999. Distribution: India (Delhi, Punjab).

Thrips coloratus Schmutz 1913. Distribution: India (Delhi, Jammu & Kashmir, Himachal Pradesh, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).

Thrips dorax Bhatti 1980. Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Thrips flavidulus (Bagnall 1923). Distribution: India (Assam, Chandigarh, Himachal Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh).

Thrips flavus Schrank 1776. Distribution: India (Delhi, Goa, Haryana, Jammu & Kashmir, Himachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Punjab, Sikkim, Tripura, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).

Thrips florum Schmutz 1913. Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Delhi, Karnataka, Punjab, widely distributed).

Thrips garuda Bhatti 1980. Distribution: India (Delhi, Punjab).

Thrips hawaiiensis (Morgan 1913). Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Assam, Delhi, Karnataka, Meghalaya, Sikkim, West Bengal, widely distributed).

- Thrips hispidus* Ananthkrishnan & Jagadish 1966. Distribution: India (Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu).
- Thrips kodaikanalensis* Ananthkrishnan & Jagadish 1966. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Thrips latis* Bhatti 1967. Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).
- Thrips levatus* Bhatti 1980. Distribution: India (Assam, Maharashtra).
- Thrips longiceps* (Bagnall 1916). Distribution: India (Meghalaya, Uttar Pradesh).
- Thrips malloti* Priesner 1934. Distribution: India (Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh).
- Thrips mirus* Bhatti 1967. Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu).
- Thrips moundi* Tyagi & Kumar 2015. Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).
- Thrips orientalis* (Bagnall 1915). Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Punjab, Tripura, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh*, West Bengal).
- Thrips pallidulus* Bagnall 1924. Distribution: India (Bihar).
- Thrips palmi* Karny 1925. Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka, Odisha*, Punjab, widely distributed).
- Thrips parvispinus* (Karny 1912). Distribution: India (Karnataka).
- Thrips rostratus* Priesner 1934. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Thrips sensarmai* Vijay Veer & Srivastava 1985. Distribution: India (West Bengal).
- Thrips simplex* (Morison 1930). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh*, Karnataka*, Tamil Nadu).
- Thrips speratus* zur Strassen 1978. Distribution: India (Delhi, Tamil Nadu).
- Thrips subnudula* (Karny 1927). Distribution: India (Delhi, Haryana, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh*, West Bengal).
- Thrips tabaci* Lindeman 1889. Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka, Meghalaya, Punjab, West Bengal, widely distributed).
- Thrips tanicus* Bhatti 1970. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Thrips taurus* Bhatti 1980. Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).
- Thrips trehernei* Priesner 1927. Distribution: India (Jammu & Kashmir, Uttar Pradesh).
- Thrips vitticornis* (Karny 1922). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Thrips xenos* Bhatti 1980. Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).
- Trichromothrips*** Priesner 1930
- Trichromothrips albus* (Bhatti 1978). Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).
- Trichromothrips alis* Bhatti 1967. Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).
- Trichromothrips arorai* Bhatti 1967. Distribution: India (Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).
- Trichromothrips falculus* Bhatti, 1999. Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh, West Bengal).
- Trichromothrips fasciatus* (Ananthkrishnan 1965). Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).
- Trichromothrips flavidus* (Bhatti 1978). Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Checklist-Thrips of India

Trichromothrips indicus (Bhatti 1978).
Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Trichromothrips nilgiricus (Ramakrishnan & Margabandhu 1939). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Trichromothrips priesneri (Bhatti 1967).
Distribution: India (Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh).

Trichromothrips similis (Ananthakrishnan 1968). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Trichromothrips walteri (J.C. Crawford 1941). Distribution: India (Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

***Tusothrips* Bhatti 1967**

Tusothrips setiprivos (Karny 1927).
Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Tusothrips sumatrensis (Karny 1925).
Distribution: India (Delhi, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Punjab, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh*, West Bengal).

Suborder Tubulifera

Family Phlaeothripidae

Subfamily Idolothripinae

***Acallurothrips* Bagnall 1921**

Acallurothrips amplus (Faure 1949).
Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

***Aesthesiothrips* Ananthakrishnan 1961**

Aesthesiothrips jatrophae Ananthakrishnan 1961. Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

***Allothrips* Hood 1908**

Allothrips bicolor Ananthakrishnan 1964.
Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh*, West Bengal).

Allothrips indicus Ananthakrishnan 1958.
Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Allothrips montanus Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).

Allothrips watsoni Hood 1939. Distribution: India (Delhi).

***Bactrothrips* Karny 1912**

Bactrothrips idolomorphus (Karny 1919).
Distribution: India (Kerala, Manipur, Uttar Pradesh).

Bactrothrips luteus Ananthakrishnan 1973.
Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

***Compsothrips* Reuter 1901**

Compsothrips congoensis (Hood 1952).
Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).

Compsothrips ramamurthii (Ananthakrishnan 1964). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).

***Diaphorothrips* Karny 1920**

Diaphorothrips unguipes Karny 1920.
Distribution: India (Karnataka, Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

***Dinothrips* Bagnall 1908**

Dinothrips juglandis Moulton 1933.
Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Dinothrips longicauda (Ananthakrishnan, 1961). Distribution: India Maharashtra.

Dinothrips spinosus (Schmutz, 1913).
Distribution: India (Karnataka, Kerala, Uttarakhand).

Dinothrips sumatrensis Bagnall, 1908. Distribution: India (Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Karnataka, Kerala, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, Tripura).

***Ethirothrips* Karny 1925**

Ethirothrips anacardii (Ananthakrishnan 1969). Distribution: India (Kerala).

Ethirothrips beelsoni (Moulton 1928). Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

Ethirothrips brevisetosus (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1970). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Kerala).

Ethirothrips brevis (Bagnall 1921). Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Ethirothrips indicus (Bagnall 1921). Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

Ethirothrips longisetis (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1970). Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Ethirothrips obscurus (Schmutz 1913). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, West Bengal).

Ethirothrips uredinis (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1970). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Ethirothrips vitreipennis (Priesner 1939). Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Kerala).

Ethirothrips *tirumalaiensis* (Ananthakrishnan 1969). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).

***Elaphrothrips* Buffa 1909**

Elaphrothrips curvipes Priesner 1929. Distribution: (Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Elaphrothrips denticollis (Bagnall 1909). Distribution: India (Assam, Karnataka, Kerala, Meghalaya, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, West Bengal).

Elaphrothrips greeni (Bagnall 1914). Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Elaphrothrips insigninis Ananthakrishnan 1973. Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).

Elaphrothrips notabilis Ananthakrishnan 1973. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Elaphrothrips procer (Schmutz 1913). Distribution: India (Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, West Bengal).

Elaphrothrips spiniceps Bagnall 1932. Distribution: India (Meghalaya, Uttar Pradesh).

***Gastrothrips* Hood 1912**

Gastrothrips acuticornis (Hood 1925). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Gastrothrips falcatus (Ananthakrishnan 1968). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Goa, Karnataka, Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Gastrothrips turbinatus (Ananthakrishnan 1967). Distribution: India (Karnataka, Tamil Nadu).

***Ischyrothrips* Schmutz 1913**

Ischyrothrips crassus Schmutz 1913. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).

***Loyolaia* Ananthakrishnan 1964**

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Loyolaia indica Ananthakrishnan 1964. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Machatothrips Bagnall 1908

Machatothrips corticosus Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Kerala).

Machatothrips indicus Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1970. Distribution: India (Karnataka, Kerala).

Machatothrips silvaticus Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).

Meiothrips Priesner 1929

Meiothrips menoni Ananthakrishnan 1964. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala).

Meiothrips nepalensis Kudo & Ananthakrishnan 1974. Distribution: India (Manipur).

Neosmerinthothrips Schmutz 1913

Neosmerinthothrips fructuum Schmutz 1913. Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Neosmerinthothrips inquilinus Ananthakrishnan 1961. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Neosmerinthothrips robustus (Ananthakrishnan 1964). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Goa, Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Nesidiothrips Mound 1974

Nesidiothrips alius (Ananthakrishnan 1970). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Kerala).

Nesothrips Kirkaldy 1907

Nesothrips brevicollis (Bagnall 1914). Distribution: India (Kerala, Madhya Pradesh).

Nesothrips lativentris (Karny 1913). Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Tripura, West Bengal).

Mecynothrips Bagnall 1908

Mecynothrips simplex Bagnall 1912. Distribution: India (Karnataka, Kerala, Manipur).

Ophthalmothrips Hood 1919

Ophthalmothrips breviceps (Bagnall 1914). Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Ophthalmothrips faurei (Ananthakrishnan 1964). Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Priesneriana Ananthakrishnan 1956

Priesneriana kabandha (Ramakrishna 1928). Distribution: India (Karnataka, Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Tiarothrips Priesner 1935

Tiarothrips subramanii (Ramakrishna 1925). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Phlaeothripinae

Ablemothrips Ananthakrishnan 1969

Ablemothrips maxillatus Ananthakrishnan 1969. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Aclystothrips Ananthakrishnan 1971

Aclystothrips aberrans Ananthakrishnan 1973. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).

Aclystothrips priesneri Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

***Adraneothrips* Hood 1925**

Adraneothrips bambusae (Ananthakrishnan 1964). Distribution: India (Kerala).

Adraneothrips disjunctus Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).

Adraneothrips elegans Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Kerala).

Adraneothrips infirmus (Ananthakrishnan 1971). Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Adraneothrips limpidus Ananthakrishnan 1964. Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Adraneothrips *madrasensis* Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Adraneothrips *nilgiriensis* (Ananthakrishnan 1971). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Adraneothrips okajimai (Muraleedharan & Sen 1981). Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Manipur, Meghalaya, Tripura).

Adraneothrips pteris (Ananthakrishnan 1971). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Adraneothrips stannardi Ananthakrishnan 1969. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

***Aeglothrips* Ananthakrishnan 1969**

Aeglothrips denticulus Ananthakrishnan 1969. Distribution: India (Kerala).

***Agrothrips* Jacot-Guillarmod 1939**

Agrothrips insolitus Ananthakrishnan 1969. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).

***Ahamothrips* Kumar, Tyagi & Bhatti 2007**

Ahamothrips maxima Kumar, Tyagi & Bhatti 2007. Distribution: India (Delhi).

***Alerothrips* Bhatti 1995**

Alerothrips indicus (Ananthakrishnan 1964). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu).

***Aleurodothrips* Franklin 1909**

Aleurodothrips fasciapennis (Franklin 1908). Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Karnataka*, Kerala, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

***Alocothrips* Priesner 1952**

Alocothrips hadrocerus (Karny 1926). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

***Alloiothrips* Ananthakrishnan 1964**

Alloiothrips nigrisetis Ananthakrishnan 1964. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

***Ananthakrishnana* Bhatti 1967**

Ananthakrishnana euphorbiae (Priesner 1931). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Maharashtra).

***Androthrips* Karny 1911**

Androthrips coimbatorensis Ramakrishna 1934. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Androthrips flavipes Schmutz 1913. Distribution: India (Assam, Kerala, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, Tripura).

Androthrips flavitibia Moulton 1933. Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Assam, Manipur, Tripura, Uttarakhand).

Androthrips melastomae (Zimmermann 1900). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Checklist-Thrips of India

Androthrips ramachandrai Karny 1926. Distribution: India (Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).

Apelaunothrips Karny 1925

Apelaunothrips bhowalii (Ananthakrishnan 1972). Distribution: India (Meghalaya, Uttar Pradesh).

Apelaunothrips consimilis (Ananthakrishnan 1969). Distribution: India (Karnataka, Kerala, Tripura).

Apelaunothrips indicus (Ananthakrishnan 1967). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Apelaunothrips lucidus (Ananthakrishnan 1965). Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Apelaunothrips madrasensis (Ananthakrishnan 1964). Distribution: India (Kerala, Manipur, Tamil Nadu).

Aphlothrips Kumar & Tyagi 2007

Aphlothrips virktamathai Kumar & Tyagi 2007. Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Apterygothrips Priesner 1933

Apterygothrips banyan Bhatti 1997. Distribution: India (Delhi).

Apterygothrips bournieri Bhatti & Mehra 1994. Distribution: India (Punjab).

Apterygothrips dempax Bhatti & Ananthakrishnan 1978. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).

Apterygothrips fungosus (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Apterygothrips hispanicus (Bagnall 1916). Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

Apterygothrips jogensis Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969). Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Apterygothrips pellucidus (Ananthakrishnan 1968). Distribution: India (Delhi*, Haryana, Tamil Nadu).

Apterygothrips rubriginosus (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1971). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Araeothrips Ananthakrishnan 1976

Araeothrips duibongensis (Nilamani & Prasad 1991). Distribution: India (Manipur).

Araeothrips longisetis Ananthakrishnan 1976. Distribution: India (Arunachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh).

Araeothrips vamana Muraleedharan 1982. Distribution: India (Manipur).

Arrhenothrips Hood 1919

Arrhenothrips acuminatus Ananthakrishnan 1969. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).

Arrhenothrips brevis Ananthakrishnan & Swaminathan 1980. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Arrhenothrips dhumrapaksha Ramakrishna 1928. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Arrhenothrips longisetis Sen 1977. Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Arrhenothrips ramakrishnae Hood 1919. Distribution: India (Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Ataliothrips Bhatti 1995

Ataliothrips reuteri (Bagnall 1913). Distribution: India (Delhi, Uttar Pradesh).

Athlibothrips Priesner 1952

Athlibothrips inquilinus (Ananthakrishnan & Varadarasan 1978). Distribution: India (Bihar).

Athlibothrips manipurensis Muraleedharan 1982. Distribution: India (Manipur).

Athlibothrips yercaudensis Muraleedharan & Sen, 198. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

***Austrothrips* Brethes 1915**

Austrothrips cochinchinensis Karny 1922. Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

***Ayyarothrips* Ananthakrishnan 1972**

Ayyarothrips abstrusus Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

***Azaleothrips* Ananthakrishnan 1964**

Azaleothrips amabilis Ananthakrishnan 1964. Distribution: India (Goa, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).

Azaleothrips aspersus Bhatti 1995. Distribution: India (Delhi, Maharashtra).

Azaleothrips bhattii Vijay Veer & Chauhan 1990. Distribution: India (Delhi, Uttarakhand).

Azaleothrips lineus Bhatti 1995. Distribution: India (Delhi, Maharashtra).

***Bamboosiella* Ananthakrishnan 1957**

Bamboosiella bicoloripes Ananthakrishnan 1957. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Bamboosiella graminella (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka).

Bamboosiella malabarica (Ananthakrishnan 1965). Distribution: India (Delhi, Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Bamboosiella microptera (Pitkin 1976). Distribution: India (Kerala).

Bamboosiella nayari (Ananthakrishnan 1958). Distribution: India (Kerala, West Bengal).

Bamboosiella varia (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969). Distribution: India (Delhi, Karnataka, Kerala, Uttarakhand, West Bengal).

Bamboosiella venkataramani Kumar & Tyagi 2014. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

***Baenothrips* Crawford 1948**

Baenothrips asper (Bournier 1963). Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Manipur, Tamil Nadu).

Baenothrips indicus (Ananthakrishnan 1966). Distribution: India (Delhi, Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Baenothrips minutus (Ananthakrishnan 1964). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

***Brachythrips* Reuter 1899**

Brachythrips dhirgavadana Ramakrishna 1928. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

***Bradythrips* Hood & Williams 1925**

Bradythrips hesperus Hood & Williams 1925. Distribution: India (Kerala).

***Bunothrips* Ananthakrishnan 1969**

Bunothrips cruralis Ananthakrishnan 1969. Distribution: India (Kerala).

***Byctothrips* Ananthakrishnan 1973**

Byctothrips ayyari Ananthakrishnan 1973. Distribution: India (Karnataka, Tamil Nadu).

***Calamothrips* Ananthakrishnan 1967**

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Calamothrips fastigiatus Ananthakrishnan 1967. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Carissothrips Ananthakrishnan 1964

Carissothrips nigrescens Ananthakrishnan 1964. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).

Chiraplothrips Priesner 1931

Chiraplothrips graminellus Priesner 1939. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Chiridothrips Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1939

Chiridothrips indicus Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1939. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Chlarathrips Ananthakrishnan 1967

Chlarathrips tersus Ananthakrishnan 1967. Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Corycidothrips Ananthakrishnan 1972

Corycidothrips inquilinus Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Kerala).

Crotonothrips Ananthakrishnan 1968

Crotonothrips cacharensis Muraleedharan & Sen 1978. Distribution: India (Assam, Tripura).

Crotonothrips coorgensis Ananthakrishnan 1976. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Crotonothrips dantahasta (Ramakrishna 1928). Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Crotonothrips davidi Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Crotonothrips dissimilis Ananthakrishnan 1976. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Crotonothrips erraticus Muraleedharan & Sen 1981. Distribution: India (Tripura).

Crotonothrips gallarum Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Crotonothrips longirostris Muraleedharan & Sen 1981. Distribution: India (Tripura).

Crotonothrips maoensis Nilamani & Prasad 1990. Distribution: India (Manipur).

Crotonothrips memecyonicus Ananthakrishnan 1976. Distribution: India (Kerala).

Crotonothrips mimicus (Ananthakrishnan 1969). Distribution: India (Kerala)

Crotonothrips nagaensis Muraleedharan 1982. Distribution: India (Manipur).

Crotonothrips nelliampathiensis Varatharajan & Chochong 2000. Distribution: India (Manipur).

Crotonothrips parvus Ananthakrishnan 1976. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Dixothrips Ananthakrishnan 1969

Dixothrips onerosus Ananthakrishnan 1969. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala).

Dolicholepta Priesner 1932

Dolicholepta flaviantennatus (Seshadri & Ananthakrishnan 1954). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Dolicholepta inquilinus Ananthakrishnan 1954. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Dolichothrips Karny 1912

Dolichothrips assimilis Priesner & Seshadri 1952. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Dolichothrips citripes (Bagnall 1921). Distribution: India (Bihar, Chandigarh, Delhi, Karnataka, Meghalaya, Odisha, West Bengal).

Dolichothrips confusus Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

- Dolichothrips fumipennis* (Bagnall, 1921).
Distribution: India (West Bengal).
- Dolichothrips indicus* (Hood 1919).
Distribution: India (Delhi*, Karnataka, Kerala, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal)
- Dolichothrips malhavii* Ananthakrishnan 1961. Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).
- Dolichothrips montanus* Ananthakrishnan 1964. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Dolichothrips nesius* Stannard 1962.
Distribution: India (Andaman Island).
- Dolichothrips ochripes* Karny 1926.
Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).
- Dolichothrips zyziphi* (Bagnall 1923).
Distribution: India (Bihar).
- Dyothrips*** Kudo 1974
- Dyothrips palleescens* (Hood, 1919).
Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).
- Ecacanthothrips*** Bagnall 1909
- Ecacanthothrips tibialis* (Ashmead 1905).
Distribution: India (Assam, Karnataka, Kerala, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Tripura, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, West Bengal).
- Eothrips*** Hood 1915
- Eothrips coimbatorensis* Ramakrishna 1928.
Distribution: India (Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu).
- Eothrips crassicornis* (Karny 1912).
Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).
- Eothrips distinctus* Ananthakrishnan 1967.
Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).
- Eothrips sirumalaiensis* Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Eugynothrips*** Priesner 1926
- Eugynothrips priesneri* Ramakrishna 1928.
Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Euoplothrips*** Hood 1918
- Euoplothrips malabaricus* Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1931. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).
- Euryaplothrips*** Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1931
- Euryaplothrips crassus* Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1931. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Eurhynchothrips*** Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1931
- Eurhynchothrips ordinarius* (Hood 1919).
Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu).
- Gigantothrips*** Zimmermann 1900
- Gigantothrips elegans* Zimmermann 1900.
Distribution: India (Bihar, Delhi, Karnataka, Mizoram, Odisha, Punjab, Tamil Nadu).
- Gigantothrips gardneri* Ananthakrishnan 1960. Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).
- Gigantothrips halidayi* (Newman 1856).
Distribution: India (Karnataka).
- Gigantothrips ochrosceles* Priesner 1952.
Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Gigantothrips nigrodentatus* (Karny 1913).
Distribution: India (Karnataka).
- Gigantothrips seshadrii* (Ananthakrishnan 1964). Distribution: India (Kerala).
- Gigantothrips tibialis* Bagnall 1921.
Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Karnataka, Kerala, Uttarakhand).
- Glubothrips*** Ananthakrishnan 1969

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Glubothrips mucidus Ananthakrishnan 1969. Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Gynaikothrips Zimmermann 1900

Gynaikothrips affinis Muraleedharan & Sen 1981. Distribution: India (Tripura).

Gynaikothrips bengalensis Ananthakrishnan 1973. Distribution: India (Karnataka, Manipur, Nagaland, Tripura, West Bengal).

Gynaikothrips cecidii Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).

Gynaikothrips flaviantennatus Moulton 1929. Distribution: India (Odisha).

Gynaikothrips gardneri (Moulton 1933). Distribution: India.

Gynaikothrips imitator Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Gynaikothrips malabaricus Ramakrishna 1928. Distribution: India (Kerala, West Bengal).

Gynaikothrips microchaetus Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Gynaikothrips rossi Sen 1980. Distribution: India (Andaman Island).

Gynaikothrips schefflericola Ananthakrishnan & Viswanath 1975. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Gynaikothrips uzeli (Zimmermann 1900). Distribution: India (Assam, Karnataka, Odisha, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Habrothrips Ananthakrishnan 1968

Habrothrips curiosus Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Haplothrips (*Haplothrips*) Amyot & Serville 1843

Haplothrips (Haplothrips) andresi Priesner 1931. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Haplothrips (Haplothrips) bagrolis Bhatti 1973. Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Haplothrips (Haplothrips) bicolor (Ananthakrishnan 1964). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).

Haplothrips (Haplothrips) ceylonicus Schmutz 1913. Distribution: India (Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Haplothrips (Haplothrips) fungulus (Ananthakrishnan 1973). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh).

Haplothrips (Haplothrips) ganglbaueri Schmutz 1913. Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Haryana, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Meghalaya, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal), .

Haplothrips (Haplothrips) gowdeyi (Franklin 1908). Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Meghalaya, Punjab, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttar Pradesh*, West Bengal).

Haplothrips (Haplothrips) hrasvamukha (Ramakrishna 1928). Distribution: India (Kerala).

Haplothrips (Haplothrips) longisetosus Ananthakrishnan 1955. Distribution: India (Kerala, Uttar Pradesh).

Haplothrips (Haplothrips) mangiferae Priesner 1930. Distribution: India (Delhi, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh).

- Haplothrips* (*Haplothrips*) *montanus* (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1970). Distribution: India (West Bengal).
- Haplothrips* (*Haplothrips*) *pirus* Bhatti 1967. Distribution: India (Delhi).
- Haplothrips* (*Haplothrips*) *reuteri* (Karny 1907). Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).
- Haplothrips* (*Haplothrips*) *tenuipennis* Bagnall 1918. Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Assam, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).
- Haplothrips* (*Haplothrips*) *trivandrensis* (Ananthakrishnan 1965). Distribution: India (Kerala).
- Haplothrips* (*Haplothrips*) *verbasci* (Osborn 1897). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Haplothrips* (*Trybomiella*) Bagnall 1926**
- Haplothrips* (*Trybomiella*) *articulosus* (Bagnall 1926). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Meghalaya, West Bengal).
- Haplothrips* (*Trybomiella*) *bagnalli* (Trybom 1910). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Haplothrips* (*Trybomiella*) *clarisetis* Priesner 1930. Distribution: India (Delhi, Gujarat, Haryana, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).
- Haplothrips* (*Trybomiella*) *nigricornis* (Bagnall 1910). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Haplothrips* (*Trybomiella*) *talpa* Priesner 1931. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).
- Haplothrips* (*Trybomiella*) *tirumalraoi* Ramakrishna & Margabandhu 1931. Distribution: India.
- Holothrips* Karny 1911**
- Holothrips* *andamanensis* (Sen 1980). Distribution: India (Andaman Island).
- Holothrips* *ananthakrishnani* Okajima 1976. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu, Tripura).
- Holothrips* *cracens* (Ananthakrishnan 1968). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Tamil Nadu).
- Holothrips* *fumidus* (Ananthakrishnan 1972). Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal).
- Holothrips* *indicus* Ananthakrishnan 1956. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Tamil Nadu).
- Holothrips* *minor* (Hood 1937). Distribution: India: (Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Tripura).
- Holothrips* *mirandus* (Ananthakrishnan 1969). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Holothrips* *nepalensis* (Pelikán 1970). Distribution: India (West Bengal).
- Holothrips* *quadrisetis* Okajima 1976. Distribution: India (West Bengal).
- Holothrips* *ruidus* (Ananthakrishnan 1969). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Holothrips* *stannardi* (Ananthakrishnan 1972). Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).
- Holothrips* *subtilis* (Ananthakrishnan 1972). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Holothrips* *typicus* (Ananthakrishnan 1967). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Hoplandrothrips* Hood 1912**
- Hoplandrothrips* *corticis* Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).
- Hoplandrothrips* *flavipes* Bagnall 1923. Distribution: India (Karnataka, Kerala, Manipur, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, West Bengal).
- Hoplandrothrips* *kudoii* Muraleedharan 1982. Distribution: India (Manipur).

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Hoplandrothrips nobilis Priesner 1939. Distribution: India (Delhi*, Kerala, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Hoplothrips Amyot & Serville 1843

Hoplothrips angusticeps (Bagnall 1910). Distribution: India (Kerala).

Hoplothrips fungosus Moulton 1928. Distribution: India (Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Hoplothrips nemorius Ananthakrishnan 1971. Distribution: India (Karnataka, Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Hoplothrips orientalis (Ananthakrishnan 1969). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).

Hoplothrips transvaalensis (Hood 1924). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu).

Idiothrips Faure 1933

Idiothrips bellus Faure 1933. Distribution: India (Delhi, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan).

Karnyothrips Watson 1923

Karnyothrips alpha Pitkin 1976. Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Karnyothrips flavipes (Jones 1912). Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Delhi, Karnataka, Kerala, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh).

Karnyothrips melaleucus (Bagnall 1911). Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Assam, Karnataka, Kerala, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Karnyothrips mucidus (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1971). Distribution: India (Kerala, West Bengal).

Karnyothrips nigriflavus Ramakrishna 1934. Distribution: India (Kerala, Tamil Nadu).

Kochummania Ananthakrishnan 1969

Kochummania excelsa Ananthakrishnan 1969. Distribution: India (Kerala).

Leeuwenia Karny 1912

Leeuwenia coriacea (Bagnall 1912). Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

Leeuwenia eugeniae Bagnall 1924. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Leeuwenia karnyiana Priesner 1929. Distribution: India (Assam, Karnataka, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal).

Leeuwenia maculans Priesner & Seshadri 1953. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Leeuwenia vorax Ananthakrishnan 1969. Distribution: India (Kerala).

Liophlaeothrips Priesner 1919

Liophlaeothrips ablusus Ananthakrishnan 1971. Distribution: India (Kerala).

Liophlaeothrips acaciae Tyagi & Kumar 2011. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Liophlaeothrips amoenus Ananthakrishnan 1966. Distribution: India (Assam, Maharashtra).

Liophlaeothrips cecidii Ananthakrishnan 1964. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Liophlaeothrips curtus Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).

Liophlaeothrips dentipes (Seshadri & Ananthakrishnan 1954). Distribution: India (Kerala).

Liophlaeothrips nitidus Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).

- Liophlaeothrips pavettae* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).
- Liophlaeothrips pictus* Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Tamil Nadu).
- Liophlaeothrips reperticus* Ananthakrishnan & Muraleedharan 1974. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Liophlaeothrips segnis* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969. Distribution: India (Londa).
- Liophlaeothrips succinctus* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969. Distribution: India (Kerala).
- Liophlaeothrips vichitravarna* (Ramakrishna 1928). Distribution: India (Karnataka, Tamil Nadu).
- Liothrips (Liothrips)* Uzel 1895**
- Liothrips (Liothrips) aberrans* Muraleedharan & Sen 1978. Distribution: India (Sikkim, West Bengal).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) abstrusus* Ananthakrishnan & Muraleedharan 1974. Distribution: India (Karnataka).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) aequilus* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) ananthakrishmani* Sen 1976. Distribution: India (Arunachal Pradesh).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) associatus* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) ater* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969. Distribution: India (Kerala).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) bireni* Nilamani & Prasad, 1991. Distribution: India (Manipur).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) bosei* Moulton 1928. Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) bournieri* Muraleedharan & Sen 1981. Distribution: India (Tripura).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) cecidii* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969. Distribution: India (Kerala).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) champakae* (Ramakrishna & Margabandhu, 1939). Distribution: India (West Bengal).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) chavicae* (Zimmermann 1900). Distribution: India (Kerala).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) clarus* Muraleedharan & Sen 1981. Distribution: India (Tripura).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) digressus* Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) emulatus* Ananthakrishnan 1976. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) epacrus* Ananthakrishnan & Muraleedharan 1974. Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) exilis* (Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969). Distribution: India (Goa).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) flavescens* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969. Distribution: India (Kerala).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) flavitibia* Moulton 1933. Distribution: India (West Bengal).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) fragilis* Ananthakrishnan 1976. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) furvus* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969. Distribution: India (Kerala).
- Liothrips (Liothrips) himalayanus* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1970.

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- Distribution: India (Meghalaya, West Bengal).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *infrequens* Muraleedharan & Sen 1981. Distribution: India (Tripura).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *indicus* Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Maharashtra).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *inquilinus* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1967. Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *infrequens* Muraleedharan & Sen 1981. Distribution: India (Tripura).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *interlocatus* (Karny 1927). Distribution: India (Kerala).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *jogensis* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1967. Distribution: India (Karnataka).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *kannani* (Moulton 1929). Distribution: India.
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *kolliensis* Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *litsaeae* Moulton 1933. Distribution: India.
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *malabaricus* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1967. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *minys* Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *monae* Nilamani & Prasad 1990. Distribution: India (Manipur).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *mohanrami* Bhatti, Varatharajan and Singh 2006. Distribution: India (Nagaland).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *morindae* Ananthakrishnan & Muraleedharan 1974. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *morulus* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1970. Distribution: India (West Bengal).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *moultoni* (Ramakrishna 1928). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *mucronis* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1967. Distribution: India (Karnataka).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *muralii* Sen 1982. Distribution: India (Kerala).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *nanus* Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *nubilis* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969. Distribution: India (Kerala).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *pallicrus* (Karny 1923). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *pallipes* (Karny 1913). Distribution: India (Kerala).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *perandaphaga* (Ramakrishna, 1928). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *ramakrishnae* Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *raoensis* (Ramakrishna, 1928). Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *renukae* Muraleedharan & Sen 1981. Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *retusus* Ananthakrishnan 1976. Distribution: India (Karnataka).
Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *sangali* Kulshrestha & Vijay Veer 1990. Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *seshadrii*
Ananthakrishnan & Muraleedharan 1974.

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *setinodis* (Reuter 1880).

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *tersus*
Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1967.

Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *tibialis* Priesner 1952.

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *variabilis*
Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1967.

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Liothrips (*Liothrips*) *wangjinensis* Nilamani
& Prasad 1991. Distribution: India
(Manipur).

Liothrips (*Zopyrothrips*) Priesner 1968

Liothrips (*Zopyrothrips*) *fumipennis* (Karny
1913). Distribution: India.

Liothrips (*Zopyrothrips*) *sordidus*
Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India
(Tamil Nadu).

Liothrips (*Zopyrothrips*) *spectabilis*
Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India
(Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu).

Liothrips (*Zopyrothrips*) *viticola* (Karny
1913). Distribution: India (Kerala).

Lygothrips Ananthakrishnan 1964

Lygothrips *jambuvasi* (Ramakrishna 1928).
Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh,
Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil
Nadu).

Macrophthalthmothrips Karny 1922

Macrophthalthmothrips *splendidus*
Ananthakrishnan 1968. Distribution: India
(Karnataka, Tamil Nadu).

Malacothrips Hinds 1902

Malacothrips *natalensis* (Trybom 1912).

Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

Mallothrips Ramakrishna 1928

Mallothrips *indica* Ramakrishna 1928.

Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh,
Delhi, Karnataka, Kerala*, Tamil Nadu).

Margaritothrips Priesner 1932

Margaritothrips *flavus* Bhatti 1965.

Distribution: India (Madhya Pradesh).

Margaritothrips *longus* Bhatti 1967.

Distribution: India (Delhi).

Margaritothrips *sumatrensis* Priesner 1932.

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Maxillithrips Bhatti 1978

Maxillithrips *arorai* (Bhatti & Hattar 1974).

Distribution: India (Haryana).

Mesicothrips Priesner 1952

Mesicothrips *inquilinus* Ananthakrishnan
1967. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Mesicothrips *plicans* Priesner 1952.

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Mesothrips Zimmermann 1900

Mesothrips *acutus* Muraleedharan & Sen
1981. Distribution: India (Tripura).

Mesothrips *ambasensis* Muraleedharan &
Sen 1981. Distribution: India (Tripura).

Mesothrips *apatelus* Karny 1927.
Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Mesothrips *bhimabahu* Ramakrishna 1928.

Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Mesothrips *cracens* Ananthakrishnan 1968.

Distribution: India (Karnataka).

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Mesothrips extensivus Ananthakrishnan & Jagadish 1969. Distribution: India (Assam, Kerala, Meghalaya, Tamil Nadu).

Mesothrips jordani Zimmermann 1900. Distribution: India (Andaman Island, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, West Bengal).

Mesothrips latus Muraleedharan & Sen 1981. Distribution: India (Tripura).

Mesothrips lividicornis (Karny 1923). Distribution: India (Tripura).

Mesothrips malloti Moulton 1929. Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

Mesothrips manii Ananthakrishnan 1972. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Mesothrips melinocnemis Karny 1927. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Mesothrips perlucidus Muraleedharan & Sen 1981. Distribution: India (Tripura).

Mimothrips Priesner 1949

Mimothrips orientalis Ananthakrishnan 1966. Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Mutothrips Ananthakrishnan & Swaminathan 1980

Mutothrips validus Ananthakrishnan & Swaminathan 1980. Distribution: India (Karnataka).

Mystrothrips Priesner 1949

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